

ISic0825

I.Sicily inscription 0825

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

natural rock

Object

rock

face

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Sella, cave, 8 miles west

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Sella, in situ

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἀριστοβούλα
2. Θεοδώρου
3. τὰ τρίκλειν[α]
4. καὶ τὸν βωμὸν
5. Νύμφαις

Apparatus

Text of IG with slight changes

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492449

EDCS 39101973

PHI 140293

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